

1 Identification of concepts of importance for the assessment of internal validity of *in vitro*
2 toxicology studies using a modified Delphi technique

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59 Disclaimers

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68 Abstract

69 **Context:** *In vitro* toxicity studies are increasingly being included as evidence in systematic
70 reviews and chemical risk assessments. INVITES-IN, a tool for assessing the internal validity of
71 *in vitro* studies, is under development in a process consisting of four consecutive studies. Study
72 One in the creation of INVITES-IN was the development of an “item bank” database of 405
73 concepts (“items”) of potential relevance for assessing the internal validity of *in vitro* toxicity
74 studies. The items were gathered from both focus group discussions and a purposive literature
75 sample. In this paper we present the second study in the creation of INVITES-IN, i.e. the
76 methods and results for identifying items for consideration when assessing the potential for bias
77 in an *in vitro* study.

78 **Method:** A two-round digital Delphi survey, followed by online Delphi panel discussions guided
79 by a moderator, was performed. The Delphi participants were experienced with both *in vitro*
80 models and systematic review methods.

81 **Results:** Fifteen experts completed both Delphi rounds, and thirteen participated in a guided
82 Delphi panel discussion. Of the 405 items in the bank, the experts agreed that 372 should be

83 considered when assessing the potential for bias in an *in vitro* study. Items gathered from both
84 the literature sample and the focus group discussions (Study One) were considered to be
85 important for the assessment of the potential for bias in an *in vitro* study; 83%-100% of the items
86 collected from the literature sample were identified to be important and 91% (127) of the new
87 items discovered in the focus group discussions of Study One were identified to be important.

88 **Discussion:**

89 The 372 retained items will be interpreted into a manageable set of study appraisal criteria and
90 a supporting guidance that will constitute the INVITES-IN study appraisal tool. In terms of
91 lessons for tool development, the high retention of items included in tools designed for
92 assessment of human and animal studies to *in vitro* studies suggests that many validity
93 concepts are generally applicable across multiple study designs. Therefore, tool development
94 processes should benefit from drawing on assessment tools outside the immediate domain of
95 interest. Tool development would also likely benefit from supplementing literature reviews with
96 focus group discussions, as our results demonstrate that the use of focus group discussions
97 with domain experts was a pragmatic and valuable approach to increasing coverage of items in
98 a tool development process.

99 In conclusion, this study demonstrates the value of using rigorous methods to ensure a
100 comprehensive dataset as the starting point for creation of an assessment tool, though the
101 direct application of Delphi methods to item banks may be an unnecessary step in tool
102 development.

103 **1 Introduction**

104 Systematic reviews have become increasingly common in toxicology, environmental health, and
105 chemical risk assessment (Menon et al., 2022). Applying systematic review principles in
106 chemical risk assessment has become an established methodology for achieving rigorous,
107 transparent and objective analysis of all evidence relating to the assessment task, with a wide
108 uptake by national and international risk assessment agencies including the U.S. Environmental
109 Protection Agency (EPA, 2022; EPA, 2023), the European Food Safety Authority (EFSA, 2010;
110 EFSA et al., 2017), and the World Health Organization (WHO, 2021). An important part of
111 systematic review methodology is assessing the internal validity of each included study, i.e. the
112 extent to which the design, conduct, and reporting of a study are likely to have prevented bias or
113 systematic error in its results or findings.

114 A challenge for systematic reviews that include *in vitro* studies, however, is that there is no
115 obviously authoritative (i.e. generally accepted as valid) tool suitable for assessing the internal
116 validity of this type of study. While several options exist for human and animal studies, the
117 development of a tool for *in vitro* studies is less advanced. Three separate reviews have
118 indicated that none of the existing appraisal tools for *in vitro* studies individually cover all critical
119 aspects for assessing the internal validity of *in vitro* studies (Barbosa et al., 2023; Tran et al.,
120 2021; Whaley et al., 2024). To address this issue, we are developing the INVITES-IN (IN VITro
121 Experimental Studies INternal validity) tool. To create a comprehensive and well-designed
122 assessment tool for *in vitro* studies, we are following the general framework for developing
123 quality assessment tools as suggested by Whiting et al. (2017) and our rigorous development
124 protocol is described in Mathisen et al. (2023) and Svendsen et al. (2023).

125 Four methodological stages that we refer to as “studies” are described in the development
126 protocols:

- 127 • Study One: Creation of a comprehensive database (“item bank”) of concepts that may be
128 relevant for the assessment of internal validity of *in vitro* toxicity testing studies, completed in
129 2023 (Vist et al., 2024).
- 130 • Study Two (the present study): Identification of items of importance for the assessment of
131 internal validity in an *in vitro* study from the item bank (Study One).
- 132 • Study Three: Creation of a beta version of INVITES-IN based on the outcome of Studies
133 One and Two.
- 134 • Study Four: Creation of the final version of INVITES-IN, incorporating insights gained from
135 user-testing of the beta version.

136 The literature sources in Study One included a purposive sample of study appraisal tools
137 (Cooper et al., 2016; EPA, 2022; Higgins et al., 2024; NTP OHAT, 2015; Roth et al., 2021;
138 Sterne et al., 2019) and an item bank (Whaley et al., 2024). In total, 405 items were included in
139 the item bank. To structure the item bank, items were organised thematically into twelve bias
140 domains, such as detection, performance, and selection bias (the bias domains and definitions
141 are available in Table 2).

142 The goal of the present study was to generate the final dataset of items from which the beta
143 version of INVITES-IN will be derived in Study Three. The present paper describes the methods

144 and results for Study Two i.e., the process for narrowing down the 405 items in the item bank
145 (Study One) by identifying the items that are of importance for assessment of internal validity of
146 *in vitro* studies. The methods and results for Study One are described in Vist et al. (2024), and
147 Study Three and Study Four will be described in a third manuscript.

148 (Note that key technical terms such as “item” are defined in the glossary at the end of this
149 manuscript.)

150 2 Methods

151 2.1 Study design

152 A modified Delphi method (Dalkey and Helmer, 1963) was applied to identify the items in the
153 item bank (Vist et al., 2024) that are of importance when assessing the potential for bias in an *in*
154 *vitro* study. The Delphi method was chosen for its ability to collect subjective expert statements
155 anonymously, promoting transparency while minimising the influence of social dynamics or
156 individual personalities on the feedback process.

157 The study included a two-round quantitative digital Delphi survey followed by online Delphi
158 panel discussions guided by a moderator from the project team (referred to as a “workshop” in
159 the protocol). The Delphi panel discussions were used to obtain agreement on items that did not
160 achieve agreement in the two-round Delphi survey. Each item was discussed in one Delphi
161 panel, and participants were invited to one guided Delphi panel discussion each. Three guided
162 Delphi panel discussions were arranged in total to enable smaller-group discussions on the
163 items to make it possible to involve all participants in the discussions.

164 A Delphi round was defined as the process in which the participants completed a questionnaire.
165 Participants had to complete the previous Delphi round to be eligible for the next, and both
166 Delphi rounds to be eligible for participation in an online guided Delphi panel discussion. The
167 data analysis was performed after each Delphi round and after the Delphi panel discussions.
168 The participants received information about the results of each Delphi round as preparation for
169 the next round or the Delphi panel discussion.

170 2.2 Participants

171 To identify items of importance for the assessment of internal validity in an *in vitro study*, we
172 considered it to be important that the participants have experience with both *in vitro* studies and
173 systematic review principles. The research team and the scientific advisory group (see “Project

174 Governance” section) nominated persons fulfilling the eligibility criteria defined in the protocol
175 (Svendsen et al., 2023):

- 176 • Active in the field of *in vitro* studies (having practical experience in conducting *in vitro*
177 studies or experience in analysing or evaluating data from such studies).
- 178 • Experience with systematic literature review principles (since the assessment of internal
179 validity is an important part of the systematic review approach).
- 180 • Affiliation in academia, governmental institutions (including risk assessment institutions and
181 research institutes) or private research institutes.
- 182 • Qualification at a post-doctoral level or higher.
- 183 • At least level B1 in English (Common European Framework of Reference for Languages
184 level).

185 Participants in the focus group discussions in Study One were not eligible for participation in the
186 Delphi study.

187 Thirty-seven eligible experts were nominated, and all were invited to participate in the Delphi
188 study. They were contacted via email and received a letter of information (Supplementary
189 materials 1). The recruitment period was September 2023 to October 2023. All participants who
190 accepted the invitation ($N = 19$) actively confirmed their consent to participate in the study and
191 were asked to fill out a short questionnaire to map geographical distribution, gender distribution,
192 and experience level. Only two persons in the research team knew the identity of the
193 participants, the one inviting the participants to the study (GHM) and the one creating the Delphi
194 questionnaires (CS).

195 2.3 The Delphi survey questionnaire

196 All items in the item bank were included in the questionnaire. One duplicate item was not
197 discovered before the start of the Delphi study; therefore, 406 items were included in the Delphi
198 survey. The questionnaire for Delphi round two included the items that did not reach agreement
199 in round 1 (see Section 2.4 for criteria for identification of agreement).

200 The two-round Delphi survey was administered through Welphi (www.welphi.com), an online
201 survey platform designed for Delphi studies. Instructions (which summarise how information
202 was presented to the participants), the survey, and contact information for the project lead were
203 provided to the participants (Supplementary materials 2). Pilot testing of the survey was
204 performed by a minimum of four persons in the research team before the start of both rounds.

205 Ideally, pilot testing would have been conducted with a sample of the population for whom the
206 survey was designed. Due to limited access to the intended sample, we opted to conduct the
207 pilot with members of the project team.

208 Participants were automatically assigned participation codes randomly generated by the Welphi
209 platform. The research team did not have a key to link the participants to the participant codes,
210 thus, all responses were anonymised to all team members.

211 2.4 Rounds one and two

212 At the start of a round, participants received an email with a link to the survey. The Welphi
213 software allowed the participants to log in and work with the survey as many times as needed
214 until the closure of the round. Round one was open from December 13, 2023, to January 24,
215 2024. Round two lasted from February 29, 2024, to April 1, 2024. Two reminder emails were
216 sent in the first round, and one reminder email was sent in the second round.

217 In both rounds, participants were requested to rate each item according to the statement “*This*
218 *item should be considered when assessing the potential for bias in an in vitro study*” using a 5-
219 point Likert scale (“strongly disagree”, “somewhat disagree”, “neither agree nor disagree”,
220 “somewhat agree”, and “strongly agree”). Participants had the opportunity to include comments
221 and suggest alternative wording of the items. In round one, participants could also suggest
222 additional bias domains and items. For each item included in round two, ratings and comments
223 provided in round one were visible for all participants. Each participant could also see their own
224 ratings from round one. We only defined “bias” for the participants as systematic error, leaving it
225 open to them how to interpret the importance of an item for introducing bias into an *in vitro*
226 study. Also, participants were recommended not spending too long time on a single item. This
227 was to capture their intuitive ratings of the items. Since we are interested in the aggregate
228 answers of the group, intuitive ratings are sufficient.

229 The criteria for identification of agreement on the importance of an item for assessment of the
230 risk of bias in *in vitro* studies were defined in the protocol (Svendensen et al., 2023):

- 231 • An item is included when at least 70% of the participants “somewhat agree” and/or “strongly
232 agree” with the statement.
- 233 • An item is excluded when at least 70% of the participants “somewhat disagree” and/or
234 “strongly disagree” with the statement.

- 235 • An item that meets neither threshold for inclusion or exclusion is advanced to the next round
236 of Delphi, i.e. round two or the guided Delphi panel discussions.

237 The analysis of survey data was blinded, i.e. participant responses were anonymised to the
238 investigators analysing the survey data. The results from the first round were analysed by three
239 investigators (GEV, HMA, PW), and items that did not reach agreement were included in the
240 questionnaire for the second round. The results from the second round were analysed by three
241 investigators (GEV, GHM, PW), and items that did not reach agreement were included in the
242 guided Delphi panel discussions.

243 Some items that marginally reached the numerical threshold for agreement in round one or
244 round two were still included in round 2 and/or discussed in a Delphi panel. This was a
245 subjective decision made by the team when they were not confident that agreement had truly
246 been reached (i.e. there was a risk of “false agreement”), even though the agreement rule was
247 technically satisfied. Examples of this included when participant comments contradicted their
248 ratings, or the distribution of responses (indicated using Excel Sparkline charts, as shown in
249 Supplemental Material 3, sheet 5) suggested to the team a potential lack of consensus that
250 should be explored in the next round of the consensus process. An overview of the participant
251 ratings and comments as well as the team judgements (includes judgements on potential “false”
252 agreements) are included in Supplementary materials 3.

253 2.5 The guided Delphi panel discussions

254 Prior to the guided Delphi panel discussions, participants received the list of items where
255 agreement was not achieved, as well as all comments for these items from rounds one and two.
256 The items were grouped under bias domains, and the guided Delphi panel discussions were
257 structured so each domain was fully discussed. This allowed discussion of all items with
258 ambiguous agreement.

259 Using Microsoft Teams, three 90-minute online guided Delphi panel discussions with three to
260 five participants each were held on May 7, 13 and 16 to enable in-depth discussion. The guided
261 Delphi panel discussions were audio-recorded and machine-transcribed using the transcribe
262 function in Microsoft Teams classic (May 2024). Each Delphi panel had a guided discussion on
263 approximately one third of the items for which no agreement had been identified. During the
264 discussion, participants were asked to give reasonings for why an item should or should not be
265 considered when assessing the potential for bias in an *in vitro* study. The guided Delphi panel
266 discussions were moderated by one investigator (PW), assisted by another (GEV), and notes

267 were taken by a third (GHM). The results were analysed by two investigators, and identification
268 of agreement on importance was based on the investigators judgement (GEV, PW). Based on
269 the issues and arguments raised in the discussion with the Delphi panel participants, the two
270 investigators decided whether the item in question should be included or excluded. Transcripts
271 from the guided Delphi panel discussions are available in Supplementary materials 5.

272 2.6 Deviations from the protocol

273 The Welphi software was used to prepare the Delphi surveys instead of using an Excel form as
274 it included several functions considered to be important, such as e.g. anonymising the Delphi
275 participants to the research team members and providing the ratings and comments from round
276 one to all participants in round two.

277 In the data analysis of the results from rounds one and two, three investigators evaluated the
278 agreement scores and comments to detect “false agreement” (see Section 2.4). When there
279 was uncertainty related to the agreement score, the item was brought forward to the next step to
280 receive additional rating and/or information from the participants.

281 The average group response and the distribution of the participant ratings of each item are
282 presented in Supplementary materials 3. The median, standard deviation and the interquartile
283 range are not reported, because the distribution of the participant ratings was considered more
284 informative to detect potential “false agreement”.

285 The deadlines for completing the surveys were more than the planned two weeks, because the
286 number of items included in the surveys was greater than originally anticipated.

287 3 Results

288 3.1 Participants and response rate

289 51% (19/37) of the invited participants accepted the invitation. One participant withdrew before
290 the study was started due to personal reasons. The participant response rates were 94%
291 (17/18) and 88% (15/17) for rounds one and two of the Delphi survey, respectively. 87% (13/15)
292 of participants participated in a Delphi panel discussion.

293 The characteristics of the 15 participants completing both rounds one and two are shown in
294 Table 1. Most participants were from Europe (60%) and North America (33%), 73% were
295 female. Most participants had extensive expertise with *in vitro* studies (80%). Experience with

296 systematic review methods was more varied, 33% reported some experience, 27% reported
 297 moderate experience, and 40% reported extensive experience.

298 **Table 1. Characteristics of the 15 participants completing Delphi rounds one and two.**

Characteristics	Number [n (%)]
<i>Geographical distribution</i>	
Europe	9 (60%)
North America	5 (33%)
South America	1 (7%)
<i>Gender</i>	
Female	11 (73%)
Male	4 (27%)
<i>Years of experience with in vitro studies</i>	
No experience	0 (0%)
1-3 years	2 (13%)
4-6 years	1 (7%)
More than 6 years	12 (80%)
<i>Experience with systematic review methods</i>	
No experience	0 (0%)
Some experience	5 (33%)
Moderate experience	4 (27%)
Extensive experience	6 (40%)

299

300 3.2 The item flow through the Delphi study

301 The Delphi process is shown in Figure 1. The results are available in .xlsx format (Microsoft
 302 Excel) in Supplementary Materials 3. This file consists of the dataset of items identified to be
 303 important for the assessment of the internal validity in *in vitro* studies (sheet 1), the full list of
 304 items included in the Delphi study (including all duplicates), with the agreement scores,
 305 investigator actions, and participant comments (sheet 2), the flow of items through the Delphi
 306 study presented per source (sheet 3), the flow of items through the Delphi study presented per
 307 bias domain (sheet 4), and the participant rating of the items in Delphi rounds one and two, and
 308 summary statistics for the ratings (sheet 5).

309 In the first round of the Delphi survey, 406 items were surveyed. Of these, 168 were included, 0
 310 items were excluded, 0 new items were suggested, and 0 items were revised. In round two, 238
 311 items were surveyed. Of these, 72 items were included, and 0 items were excluded. 166 items
 312 were then discussed in the Delphi panels, of which 33 items were excluded (1 duplicate item
 313 included in error was also removed). This left a total of 373 items for inclusion in Study Three of
 314 the INVITES-IN development process.

315

316 **Figure 1. A flow chart of the Delphi process for identifying important items for**
 317 **assessment of internal validity in *in vitro* studies.**

318 Figure 2 illustrates the flow of items through the Delphi study with information on the source of
 319 the items (literature or focus group discussions) and the grouping of the items into bias
 320 domains. The definitions of the bias domains are included in Table 2. The code for generating

321 the Sankey plot in Figure 2 is available in Supplementary materials 4. ROBINS-E, a tool for
 322 assessment of potential biases in results from epidemiological cohort studies, had the lowest
 323 percentage of inclusion of items extracted from a source (83%). The inclusion of items from the
 324 other literature sources ranged from 95 to 100%. The inclusion of items discovered in the focus
 325 group discussions in Study One were 91% (the number of items for all bias domains are
 326 available in Table 2, the number of items for all sources are available in Table 3).

327
 328 **Figure 2. Flow of items considered through the Delphi process, disaggregated by source**
 329 **and bias domain.** The results from Delphi round one (R1), Delphi round two (R2), and the
 330 guided Delphi panel discussions (Workshop). FGD: Focus group discussions. For source
 331 information and citations, see Table 3.

332 The Sankey Plot was generated using R packages: openxlsx (Schauberg and Walker, 2025),
 333 ggplot2 (Wickham, 2016), tidyverse (Wickham et al., 2019), and a ggsanky package (Sjoberg,
 334 2024), which required installation of the devtools package (Wickham et al., 2022).

335 Table 2 shows the number of items considered in each stage of the Delphi process, organised
336 by bias domain. For each domain except “choice of question bias”, over 90% of items were
337 included as being important for assessing the potential for bias of an *in vitro* study. The bias
338 domains and definitions are primarily taken from a prerelease version of the Scientific Evidence
339 Code System (SEVCO) research methods ontology (Alper et al., 2021; FEvIR Platform Version
340 0.80.0, 06.12.2022). We modified one SEVCO bias domain (changing “Early study termination
341 bias” SEVCO:00370 to “Timing of study termination bias”), and two bias domains added
342 (“Metabias” and “Other”). Table 3 shows the number of items assessed in each stage of the
343 Delphi process, organised by source.

344 **Table 2. Items considered in the Delphi process, organised by bias domain.** (Alper et al., 2021; FEvIR Platform Version 0.80.0,
 345 06.12.2022)

Bias domain	Definition	Items considered by the Delphi participants (n)	Items included after the complete Delphi [n (%)]
Analysis bias	A bias related to the analytic process applied to the data.	55	51 (93%)
Attrition bias	A bias due to absence of expected participation or data collection after selection for study inclusion.	24	22 (92%)
Choice-of-Question bias	A bias in research design in which the research question (that the study is designed to answer) is inappropriate for the context.	5	1 (20%)
Conflicted interest bias	A bias in which decision makers influencing research design, conduct, analysis or reporting have goals or motivations that conflict with scientific research objectives.	8	8 (100%)
Confounding covariate bias	A situation in which the effect or association between an exposure or outcome is distorted by another variable. For confounding covariate bias to occur the distorting variable must be (1) associated with the exposure and the outcome, (2) not in the causal pathway between exposure and outcome, and (3) unequally distributed between the groups being compared.	7	7 (100%)
Detection bias	A bias due to distortions in any process involved in the determination of the recorded values for a variable.	104	97 (93%)
Metabias	A general distorting influence on investigator decision-making that may bias the results or findings of a study	29	28 (97%)

Other	A distortion in results due to factors other than those described in the SEVCO terms	5	5 (100%)
Performance bias	A bias resulting from differences between the received exposure and the intended exposure.	77	72 (94%)
Reporting bias	A bias due to distortions in the selection of or representation of information in study results or research findings.	18	18 (100%)
Selection bias	A bias resulting from methods used to select subjects or data, factors that influence initial study participation, or differences between the study sample and the population of interest	70	60 (86%)
Timing of Study Termination bias	A bias due to the decision to end the study earlier or later than planned.	3	3 (100%)
Total (sum)		405	372

346

347 **Table 3. Items considered in the Delphi process, organised by source.** Since some items were collected from more than one
348 source, the total number of items in this table is 497 (the number of items in the item bank before removal of duplicates).

Source, ID and information		Items considered by the Delphi participants (n)	Items included after the complete Delphi [n (%)]	Source Citation
Cooper	A study sensitivity assessment tool	21	21 (100%)	Cooper et al. (2016)
FGD	The Focus group discussions (Study One)	139	127 (91%)	Vist et al. (2024)

IRIS	An integrated risk information system	43	42 (98%)	EPA (2022)
OHAT	A handbook for conducting systematic reviews for health effects evaluations	45	43 (96%)	NTP OHAT (2015)
ROB-2	Version 2 of the Cochrane risk-of-bias tool for randomized trials	48	46 (96%)	Sterne et al. (2019)
ROBINS-E	A tool to assess risk of bias in non-randomized follow-up studies of exposure effects	69	57 (83%)	Higgins et al. (2024)
SciRAP	A tool for evaluation of toxicity data for Risk Assessment and Policy	36	36 (100%)	Roth et al. (2021)
Whaley	An item bank for <i>in vitro</i> studies	96	91 (95%)	Whaley et al. (2024)

350 4 Discussion

351 We performed a two round digital Delphi survey followed by online Delphi panel discussions
352 guided by a moderator from the project team to identify items that should be considered when
353 assessing the potential for bias in an *in vitro* study. The INVITES-IN item bank (Vist et al.,
354 2024), consisting of 405 items, was the basis for the Delphi study. The Delphi participants
355 agreed that 372 (92%) of these items should be considered when assessing the potential for
356 bias in an *in vitro* study, whereas only 33 should not be considered.

357 4.1 Strengths and limitations of the Delphi study

358 4.1.1 Number of Delphi rounds

359 The workload for the Delphi participants was extensive, with 406 items included in the round
360 one questionnaire and 238 in the round two questionnaire. Although Delphi rounds can be
361 repeated until agreement among participants is reached, we decided to arrange guided Delphi
362 panels for discussion of the items where agreement was not achieved in two Delphi rounds
363 instead of including more Delphi rounds. This was partly because we considered it to be more
364 efficient, and partly to avoid drop-outs since the surveys were long and time consuming.

365 4.1.2 Participants and response rates

366 Based on a study by Akins et al. (2005), we considered 15 participants to be the minimum
367 number needed for our Delphi study. Most participants in this Delphi study were from Europe
368 and North America (93%). While better geographical inclusivity was desired, we are uncertain
369 about the impact this has on the validity of our study. Most participants claimed to have
370 extensive experience with *in vitro* studies, whereas the level of experience with systematic
371 review methods was more varied, being fairly evenly distributed between “some”, “moderate”
372 and “extensive”. We are unsure whether it would have had any effect on our results if more
373 people had extensive systematic review experience.

374 It has been shown that long surveys are likely to induce respondent fatigue and reduce the
375 response rates (Gargon et al., 2019; Jeong D. et al., 2023), which may explain the drop-out of
376 three participants during round one and round two. We considered our response rates for Delphi
377 round one and two on 94% and 88%, respectively, to be acceptable. According to Akins et al.
378 (2005), based on healthcare Delphi study response rates found in the literature, a response rate
379 of 70% could be expected.

380 Participation in a guided Delphi panel discussion was desired but not a requirement for
381 participation in the Delphi study. We considered participation of 13 out of 15 Delphi participants
382 in the follow-up Delphi panel discussions to be a reasonable retention rate. Overall, while drop-
383 outs did affect agreement scores and may have explained a small number of inclusion
384 decisions, we do not believe drop-out rates had an important effect on the validity of our Delphi
385 process.

386 4.1.3 Threshold for agreement

387 We acknowledge that the threshold value has a large impact on the identification of agreement.
388 Webbe et al. (2023) demonstrated the importance of having predefined criteria for identification
389 of consensus. Our criteria for identification of agreement on the importance of an item for
390 assessment of the risk of bias in *in vitro* studies were defined in the protocol (Svendson et al.,
391 2023). Also, Webbe et al. (2023) concluded that at present it is unclear whether an optimal
392 definition of consensus criteria exists. The threshold for agreement was set relatively low for
393 inclusion and relatively high for exclusion on the assumption that the base level of consensus
394 about the importance of a given item was likely to be relatively low and highly contingent on the
395 specific experience and knowledge of a participant, such that even half of participants agreeing
396 an item is important would likely be enough that it should be considered in an eventual tool,
397 while half of participants disagreeing that an item should be included should not necessarily be
398 grounds for excluding it. We believe this consideration, along with our understanding that our
399 sample of experts is not comprehensive, justifies our inclusive thresholds.

400 4.2 Applicability of concepts included in tools designed for assessment of human and animal 401 studies to *in vitro* studies

402 We used assessment tools designed for humans and animal studies for the development of the
403 item bank, based on the assumption that they may contain concepts that are applicable to *in*
404 *vitro* studies (Vist et al., 2024). The applicability of concepts used for evaluation of risk of bias
405 across different study types was also suggested in a report by the National Academies of
406 Sciences, Engineering, and Medicine (NASEM, 2023). Here, tool developers were
407 recommended to identify risk of bias concepts from human and animal toxicity studies and to
408 use these in the development of approaches for evaluation of other study types. Although the
409 items will need to be interpreted to precisely match the *in vitro* appraisal context in the final
410 INVITES-IN tool, the high proportion of retained items in the Delphi study from the different item
411 bank sources (83% - 100%; Table 3) supports the assumption that concepts used for evaluation
412 of risk of bias are applicable across different study types.

413 4.3 Coverage of items of importance for validity assessment of *in vitro* studies by existing tools

414 More than 100 of the 405 items in the item bank were not found in the literature sources
415 sampled but were identified by 20 *in vitro* experts during focus group discussions in Study One
416 (Vist et al., 2024). Some examples of items identified in the focus group discussions included
417 “Method for fitting curves to data”, “Set of reference chemicals”, and “Adjustment for cellular
418 growth rates between groups”. The present study shows that a different group of experts agreed
419 that more than 90% of these new items are important for the assessment of the potential for
420 bias in an *in vitro* study.

421 While it is theoretically possible that a fully comprehensive tool for assessment of the internal
422 validity of *in vitro* studies already exists, three existing systematic reviews (Barbosa et al., 2023;
423 Tran et al., 2021; Whaley et al., 2024) have not found one and nobody involved in our project
424 (either project team or advisory board) were aware of one. It therefore seems unlikely that a
425 literature sampling strategy on its own is sufficient for ensuring comprehensive coverage of
426 relevant concepts when developing an internal validity assessment tool. Given the practical
427 challenges of comprehensively reviewing the literature, we believe it is a sound pragmatic
428 choice for tool developers to supplement purposive literature samples with focus group
429 discussions. We believe the high rate of retention of items from focus groups through the Delphi
430 process supports this choice.

431 4.4 Elimination of few items by Delphi

432 Strikingly few items (n=33) were eliminated by our Delphi process. One explanation is that our
433 Delphi process might have retained items of low relevance for assessing the internal validity of
434 *in vitro* toxicity studies, due to a combination of our inclusive threshold for retaining items, and a
435 possible tendency for items that were confusing to participants not being eliminated.

436 As we discussed in section 4.2, we view the relatively low threshold for agreement as desirable.
437 The length of the survey, given the number of items, seems unavoidable. In terms of confusion,
438 it is clear from Delphi comments and scores that participants were unclear as to what many
439 items meant. Also, the similarity across some items may have been challenging for the
440 participants. As investigators, we believe this is a consequence of participants being presented
441 with decontextualized items in the absence of a specific task. When discussed in the Delphi
442 panels, with the possibility to explore what the items mean, agreement was more readily
443 attainable.

444 On the other hand, it may anyway be expected that the retention rate for items would be high.
445 The item bank sources already represent a degree of expert consensus about what matters in
446 terms of introduction of bias to studies, and it therefore seems likely that a separate group of
447 experts would agree with the experts who made the original tools and participated in the focus
448 groups.

449 4.5 Lessons learned and recommendations for tool developers

450 The overall goal of this project is the development of a tool for assessment of internal validity of
451 *in vitro* studies. We have aggregated a large number of existing concepts from the literature as
452 well as developed some novel concepts from the focus groups, and all are included in an item
453 bank (Vist et al., 2024). The overall aim of this study was to identify the items that should be
454 considered when developing the tool. To this end, we expected that the 405 items in the item
455 bank would be reduced by the Delphi process to a smaller set of key items. This did not occur,
456 and we only eliminated 8% of the items. The fact that we eliminated few items, the participant
457 confusion about being presented with decontextualised items in a written survey, and the
458 theoretical reason for expecting agreement rate on items to be high, in combination suggests
459 that applying a Delphi process to an item bank may not be the most efficient way to move
460 forward in designing a bias assessment tool. If we were to repeat this exercise, instead of using
461 a Delphi process to select items for inclusion in the tool we would first analyse the concepts
462 represented by the items in the item bank, interpret the results into study appraisal criteria, and
463 then subject the appraisal criteria to a Delphi process. For INVITES-IN, the concepts will be
464 analysed in Study Three before the draft tool is created, and participants in the focus groups (in
465 Study One) will be invited to give feedback on the draft tool before the user testing in Study
466 Four. The creation of the item bank itself, especially if it includes focus group discussions,
467 remains highly valuable.

468 5 Conclusion

469 Of 405 items, 372 were agreed on by the Delphi process as being important when assessing
470 the potential for bias in an *in vitro* study. Thus, the Delphi process only eliminated a low number
471 of items. The 372 retained items will be interpreted into a manageable set of study appraisal
472 criteria and a supporting guidance that will constitute the INVITES-IN study appraisal tool.

473 Our work supports the contention that many items included in tools designed for the
474 assessment of the internal validity of human and animal studies are broadly applicable to the
475 assessment of *in vitro* studies. Our work also supports the contention that a purely literature-

476 based approach to identifying bias items is unlikely to be comprehensive, and that the use of
477 focus group discussions with experts is a pragmatic and valuable approach to increasing
478 coverage of items in a tool development process.

479 In conclusion, this study demonstrates the value of using rigorous methods to ensure a
480 comprehensive dataset as the starting point for creation of an assessment tool.

481 [Project governance](#)

482 This study is part of the project “Next Generation Risk Assessment in Practice” (VKM, 2023),
483 included in the European Partnership for the Assessment of Risks from Chemicals (PARC)
484 ([PARC, 2023](#)). A research team is responsible for the creation of INVITES-IN. A scientific
485 advisory group consisting of experts in methods for tool development, systematic review
486 methods, chemical risk assessment, toxicology, and/or *in vitro* models has been established to
487 provide the research team with strategic guidance and support during the process of creating
488 INVITES-IN (VKM, 2023).

489 [Definitions /Glossary](#)

490 These definitions have been updated since publication of our study protocol (Svendson et al.,
491 2023).

492 **Bias** is a systematic error, or deviation from the truth, in the results or findings of individual
493 studies or across studies. Systematic errors may be introduced through limitations in the design,
494 conduct, or reporting of a study.

495 **Bias domains** are a conceptual framework for thematically organising the limitations in conduct,
496 design, or reporting of a study that may affect the internal validity of a study. Bias domains in the
497 present study include but are not limited to detection, performance, and selection bias.

498 **Internal validity** is the extent to which the design, conduct, and reporting of a study is likely to
499 have prevented bias.

500 **Items** are linguistically minimalist expressions of study assessment concepts. In the INVITES-IN
501 tool development methodology, “items” are derived from study assessment criteria collected
502 from study appraisal tools and focus group discussions, that potentially relate to the internal
503 validity of an *in vitro* study.

504 **Item bank** is a database of items.

505 **Risk of bias** is the potential for systematic error in the results or findings of a study or across
506 studies. Tools for assessing the internal validity of studies tend to focus on risk of bias, as bias
507 itself cannot usually be directly measured.

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